

Geographic Variation of Morphological Characters in *Puntius lateristriga* (Valenciennes, 1842) From Sumatra and the Adjacent Island

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ABSTRACT

Puntius lateristriga (Valenciennes, 1842) is a tropical freshwater fish belonging to the Cyprinidae. Intraspecific variation among *P. lateristriga* from Sumatra Island and Singkep as adjacent island was studied based on 23 morphological characters by using UPGMA (*Unweighted Pair Group Method Arithmetic Average*) analysis. The data consist of new data from west Sumatra subpopulations (valley of mount Tujuh) and the old data from Haryono's report (Aceh, Sekundur, Bahorok, Lampung and Singkep). The study aimed to analysis the morphological characters variation of *P. lateristriga* in Sumatra and the adjacent island populations. The present results show that there are morphological variation on characters of *P. lateristriga*. *P. lateristriga* from west Sumatra which represent the middle part of Sumatra population closely related to *P. lateristriga* from Singkep island with 0.10 Euclidean distance and hold in one cluster with Lampung population which represent the south part of Sumatra population, while the Aceh, Sekundur and Bahorok populations which represent the north part of Sumatra populations were existed in another one cluster. Geologically active regions create many geographically isolated areas which can reflect in morphological characters of *P. lateristriga*.

Keywords: Geographic; morphology; Cyprinidae

1 INTRODUCTION

Puntius is a genus of cyprinids, widespread in Sumatra, Bangka Belitung, Singkep, Java and Malaysia (Weber and Beaufort, 1916; Roberts, 1989), while Taki *et al.* (1978) wrote that *Puntius* occur throughout the region from Pakistan to southern China, inhabiting various types of fresh waters. *Puntius* consist of some species with interesting colour pattern. One of the species from this genus is *Puntius lateristriga* (Valenciennes, 1842). Fish of this species has colour pattern with a broad longitudinal stripe in addition to two cross band. *P. lateristriga* is a synonym to *Barbus lateristriga* (Valenciennes, 1842) and *Systomus lateristriga* (Valenciennes, 1842). According to Weber & Beaufort (1916) and Kottelat *et al.* (1993), this species distributed in Sundaland and their colour pattern showed geographically and ontogenetically variation. Tweedie (1961) found the variation of color pattern of six populations in Malaysia and found black reduction of colour pattern on the populations at the north of Kedah and Perlis. Other than high variation of colour pattern, morphological variation also exists in this species. Haryono (2001) found the existence of morphological and pattern of the color variations of *P. lateristriga* population in five places in Sumatra that is Aceh, Sekundur, Bahorok, Lampung and Singkep. Aceh, Sekundur and Bahorok were located at the north of Sumatra; Lampung was at the south of Sumatra while Singkep was an Island close to east Sumatra Island at the middle part (Figure 1.). There is no data from west or the middle part of Sumatra included in that report.

Sumatra is a unique island, at least there are two main barrier in Sumatra, first is Bukit Barisan mountain range that predicted formed around 2.5 million years ago (Miosen) and second is the eruption of Toba mount, as the biggest eruption in world history around 71.000 years ago and caused disruption of Bukit Barisan corridor (Hamilton, 1979; Whitten *et al.*, 1987). Bukit Barisan

mountain range divided the island becomes west and east Sumatra as unequally parts, and the north and the south parts of Sumatra could be influence by Toba eruption. It was predicted that so many variation of fresh water fish in Sumatra according to its geography history. In other to complete the information and to analyze the variation of morphology characters of *P. lateristriga* in Sumatra and the adjacent island we used the Haryono's data (2001) instead of our new data from west Sumatra subpopulations. The study aimed to analyze the morphological variation of *P. lateristriga* in Sumatra and the adjacent island populations.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Fish collection was made along 600-meters on each of six rivers in the valley of Mount of Tujuh in West Sumatra using standard procedures according to Cailliet *et al.* (1996) and specimens handling followed to procedures of Kottelat *et al.* (1993). Our new data were measured from 48 individuals while Haryono (2001) data as comparison initially from Sekundur (6 individuals), Bohorok (6 individuals), Aceh (2 individuals), Lampung (12 individuals) and Singkep Island (8 individuals). The distribution of samples is enclosed in Figure 1.

Figure 1. The location of samples of data (Note: 1. Aceh; 2. Sekundur; 3. Bohorok; 4. West Sumatra; 5. Singkep Island; dan 6. Lampung)

Each individual was measured based on Strauss and Bookstein (1982) with modification to nearest 0.1 mm using digital calipers on 23 morphometric characters. Those characters were also followed as Haryono (2001) did (Figure 2.). There were Total Length (TL), Standard Length (SL), Head Length (HL), Pre Dorsal Length (PDL), Pre Pelvic Length (PPL), Pre Anal Length (PAL), Head Depth (HD), Body Height (BD), Depth of Caudal Peduncle (DCP), Length of Caudal Peduncle (LCP), Snout Length (SNL), Body Width (BW), Eye Diameter (ED), Inter Orbital Width (IW), Length of Dorsal Base (LDB), Length of Anal Base (LAB), Length of Pelvic (LPVF), Length of Pectoral (LPCF), Length of Upper Caudal (LUCL), Length of Middle Caudal (LMCR), Length of Lower Caudal (LLCL), Maxillary Barbell Length (MXB), and Snout Barbell Length (SNB).

Figure 2. Morphometric characters measurement (Haryono, 2001)

The measured characters were transformed to percent of standard length (SL) and to common logarithms. In order to analyze the relationship of *P. lateristriga* population in Sumatra and the adjacent island based on new and Haryono (2001) data, cluster analysis was done by using NTSyst Ver. 2.0.2i program (Rohlf, 1998).

RESULT

The result of the measurement of 23 characters morphometric included in Table 1. The data consist of Haryono's (2001) data from Aceh, Sekundur, Bahorok, Lampung, Singkep and from west Sumatra as a new data.

	ACEH n=2		SEKUNDUR n=6		BAHOROK n=6		LAMPUNG n=12		SINGKEP n=8		WEST SUMATRA n=48	
TL	134.02	± 0.83	130.43	± 1.99	134.89	± 1.78	132.38	± 1.37	131.52	± 2.81	133.25	± 0.22
SL	80.51	± 10.45	80.02	± 7.48	63.67	± 6.75	64.62	± 4.59	78.60	± 10.59	66.81	± 15.47
HL	29.78	± 2.39	28.02	± 1.46	29.18	± 1.44	29.74	± 2.01	25.17	± 4.91	27.01	± 0.02
PDL	51.71	± 0.37	54.50	± 0.96	55.33	± 1.22	54.22	± 1.16	53.49	± 1.25	51.14	± 0.04
PPL	55.36	± 0.19	50.82	± 1.65	49.61	± 6.55	53.35	± 1.55	51.73	± 1.51	50.72	± 0.02
PAL	76.91	± 1.28	74.93	± 1.15	74.62	± 1.35	76.26	± 1.61	75.89	± 1.77	74.15	± 0.02
HD	27.24	± 1.60	24.90	± 1.20	24.31	± 0.75	24.31	± 1.55	25.02	± 1.27	23.44	± 0.05
BD	41.80	± 0.25	39.65	± 1.61	40.89	± 2.36	40.13	± 1.19	40.77	± 0.87	39.41	± 0.03
DCP	14.60	± 0.34	14.85	± 0.33	15.74	± 0.70	15.79	± 0.39	15.24	± 0.44	16.24	± 0.01
LCP	19.30	± 1.88	19.47	± 1.65	18.06	± 0.55	17.62	± 1.04	17.93	± 1.24	19.48	± 0.02
SNL	9.46	± 0.89	9.17	± 0.64	9.41	± 0.27	9.63	± 0.91	9.78	± 0.97	7.35	± 0.01
BW	19.38	± 0.92	19.85	± 1.37	19.44	± 1.07	19.69	± 1.54	20.37	± 1.63	14.91	± 0.03
ED	7.24	± 0.24	7.39	± 0.56	8.13	± 0.57	7.99	± 0.36	6.91	± 0.55	8.06	± 0.01
IW	11.13	± 0.86	11.09	± 0.49	11.01	± 0.41	10.79	± 0.30	10.92	± 0.52	10.90	± 0.01
LDB	20.43	± 0.29	19.82	± 1.93	21.38	± 1.62	21.68	± 0.85	21.74	± 0.53	19.48	± 0.02
LAB	10.57	± 0.13	10.08	± 0.62	10.97	± 1.07	11.84	± 0.70	11.07	± 0.60	9.85	± 0.01
LPVF	22.41	± 0.49	21.48	± 1.02	22.99	± 0.91	21.54	± 0.71	20.17	± 0.63	6.23	± 0.01
LPCF	24.63	± 0.28	23.68	± 1.15	24.92	± 0.38	22.26	± 0.51	21.60	± 1.61	23.35	± 0.02
LUCL	34.07	± 0.18	30.70	± 1.46	33.57	± 1.05	34.21	± 1.53	31.74	± 1.85	30.83	± 0.03
LMCR	15.59	± 1.48	15.04	± 0.62	16.61	± 1.32	16.32	± 1.37	17.20	± 1.93	13.85	± 0.02

Table 1. Morphometric characters measurement of *P. lateristriga* new and Haryono (2001) data

The Total Length of *P. lateristriga* ranges from 130.43-134.89 mm and Standard Length from 63.67-80.51 mm. Based on the characters that have been measured, there was character divergence between populations. Those characters were: Standard Length (SL), Pre Pelvic Length (PPL), Body Width (BW), Length of Pelvic (LPVF), Length of Lower Caudal (LLCL) and Maxillary Barbell Length (MXB). To ascertain the existence of this character divergence, the analysis statistic such as Kruskal-Wallis and Mann-Whitney test to be needed. Because of acquirement data from Haryono (2001) was incomplete, and then prediction was conducted based on the result of analysis at level subpopulation of *P. lateristriga* in west Sumatra (Roesma, Chornelia & Putra, 2014 (unpublished). Analysis Kruskal-Wallis at those six subpopulations showed the character divergence between them. There were six characters found that experience of divergence that is Head Length (HL), Pre Anal Length (PAL), Depth of Caudal Peduncle (DCP), Body Width (BW), Eye Diameter (ED) and Length of Middle Caudal (LMCR). Analysis with Mann-Whitney test at subpopulations showed 1-8 characters differ between rivers in west Sumatra (subpopulations from six rivers).

Based on the value of Euclidean distance between six population of *P. lateristriga* in Sumatra and the adjacent island (Table 2.), it can be concluded that based on morphological characters, the most closely related populations was between *P. lateristriga* from West Sumatra and Singkep (0.10), followed by Bahorok-Sekundur (0.118) and Sekundur-Aceh (0.158). The smaller Euclidean distance value, the closer their relationship.

Tabel 2. Euclidean distance between six populations of *P. lateristriga* in Sumatra and the adjacent island.

Population	Aceh	Sekundur	Bahorok	Lampung	Singkep	WestSumatra
Aceh	-					
Sekundur	0.158	-				
Bahorok	0.58	0.118	-			
Lampung	0.21	0.21	0.21	-		
Singkep	0.21	0.21	0.21	0.14	-	
WestSum	0.21	0.21	0.21	0.14	0.10	-

Figure 3. show the result of UPGMA analysis on 23 morphological characters. There were two main cluster, first consist of *P. lateristriga* from West Sumatra, Singkep Island and Lampung, second consist of population from Aceh, Sekundur, and Bahorok. The Euclidean distance between those two groups was 0.21 (Table 2). All populations on each cluster also tend to subdividing, the first cluster was West Sumatra and Singkep populations held-up with Lampung population, and second cluster was Bahorok and Sekundur populations held-up with Aceh population.

Figure 3. Dendrogram of *P. lateristriga* between populations in Sumatra and adjacent island.

DISCUSSION

The existence of characters variation of morphology that found between *P. lateristriga* subpopulation in six rivers in West Sumatra (Roesma *et al.* 2014 unpublished) suggested that character divergence between populations were happened in Sumatera. Base on characters comparison that experience of divergence at subpopulation in west Sumatra and populations in the north and south Sumatra and Singkep Island, the Body Width (BW) was a character that constantly showed divergence between populations. It was predicted that those variation of character morphology caused of environmental pressure which vary geographically. It has been reported that the differences at body size character can be triggered by predator (Bronmark and Miner, 1992), territorial water condition (lotic or bentic) (Day *et al.*, 1994), temperature difference between rivers (Beacham, 1990) and food type and way to eat (Day, *et al.*, 1994; Robinson and Wilson, 1996).

According to Kondrashov and Kondrashov (1951) the characters variation of morphology that happened inter populations could be triggered by the process of speciation that caused by reproduction insulation. Losos and Glor (2003) stated that besides reproduction insulation, geographical insulation also supports the variation that tends to make subspecies or new species. Haryono (2001) concluded that pattern of widespread and morphology variation that emerges were caused by the different interregional of physical environment. There for it could be assumed that the primary factors which result in character divergence between populations are geographical factor, reproduction insulation and physical pressure from environment. According to Krukk (1999), the pressure of physical environment factors can result in divergence at individual in interpopulation. Those factors can be in form of ecological selection, sexual selection and natural selection. As a consequence, adaptation to the environment will be done and adaptation or non adaptation process could be happen. According to Haryono (2001) the environmentally pressure which produce changes and adjustments is physical factor like water temperature, pH, salinities, water brightness, water current, altitude and others. Thompson (1991) state that the factors of physical environment influence the phenotype as a consequence of genotype response to the different of environmental pressure. De Silva and Liyanage (2006) state that the environmental factor that affect on *Puntius* variation of morphology character is altitude either between different rivers or same river and that condition called as morphological plasticity.

Variations of morphology character made a cluster between populations. Analysis cluster is conducted to know the value of distance Euclidean between populations (Tables 2, Figure 3). There is a tendency that geographical distance has positive correlation by distance Euclidean. The bigger geographical distance, the bigger value of distance Euclidean and vice versa. The smaller value of

the distance Euclidean indicates that the variation of characters morphology between population getting smaller. Bernatchez *et al.*(1992) state that subdividing a population into cluster can be caused by life-history and dissociation process that happened because of process geologic millions year ago. According to Taki (1978), that existence of equality in one cluster can be assumed that they have common ancestors. There for, there is a possibility that subdividing between population in one species resulted from sharing common ancestor, nevertheless disjointed by geological process and history biogeography of Sumatra millions year ago.

Sumatera is an unstable land that disjointed at a period of Pleistocene, formed because of continuously interaction between physical factor, land/ground and climate (Hamilton, 1979 and Whitten *et al.*, 1987). In the beginning of Miocene, formed of Bukit Barisan mountain range divide the island into two unequal part and condition. This unsymmetrical part is also affected by activities of volcanic in mountain range; as a consequence the cycle of hydrology in Sumatra is varying. The western rivers relative short and flows to the West coast of Sumatra while the eastern rivers relative sloping, wide, length and flows to Sea of South Chinese (Figure 1) (Whitten *et al.*, 1987 and Colombijn, 2005). Geologically active regions create many geographically isolated areas and followed by various ecosystem conditions.

It is interesting to study more detail about this spesies, why the population in west Sumatra and Singkep Island has a smaller Euclidean distance than other part of Sumatra. Do Bukit Barisan mountain range and Toba eruption could be affect in morphology and genetic of others fresh water fish in the north and the south parts of Sumatra.

CONCLUSION

There are geographic variation of morphological characters in *P. lateristriga* in Sumatra and the adjacent island. The results of analysis show that *P. lateristriga* from west Sumatra which represent the middle part of Sumatra population closely related to *P. lateristriga* from Singkep island with 0.10 Euclidean distance and hold in one cluster with Lampung population which represent the south part of Sumatra population, while the Aceh, Sekundur and Bahorok populations which represent the north part of Sumatra populations were existed in another one cluster

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS :

We wish to express our thanks to Manager and staff of Tidar Kerinci Agung Company for the grant and facilities, to Mr. Haryono for the data on paper, and to Dr. Wilson Novarino and team for their collaboration.

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